

Impact of Co-digestion and Slurry concentration on biogas production from Kitchen wastes of *Musa paradisiaca* (Unripe plantain fruit peels) and *Phaseolus vulgaris* (Bean peels).

Justin Chikezie Nnokwe ^{1,*}, Michael Uchenna Orji ², Lawrencina Anayochi Adjeroh ¹ and James Idara Bassey ³

¹ Department of Biology, Federal University of Technology, Owerri, Imo State, Nigeria.

² Department of Applied Microbiology and Brewing, Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka, Anambra State, Nigeria.

³ Department of Biotechnology, Federal University of Technology, Owerri, Imo State, Nigeria.

World Journal of Advanced Research and Reviews, 2024, 24(02), 803–807

Publication history: Received on 27 September 2024; revised on 05 November 2024; accepted on 08 November 2024

Article DOI: <https://doi.org/10.30574/wjarr.2024.24.2.3383>

Abstract

The efficient and useful conversion of kitchen waste into biogas will mitigate the health and environmental challenges caused by their indiscriminate disposal. This study compared the potential yields of biogas from plantain peels chaff (P) and bean peels chaff (B) when anaerobically digested in singles and when combined, and when digested in different slurry concentrations. Two combinations of the substrates were used; PB1 consisted of P and B combined in the ratio of 1:0.691 respectively, while PB2 had an equal ratio (1:1) of P and B. The substrates were digested anaerobically in three slurry concentrations representing substrate/water mixing ratios of 1:5 (S1), 1:10 (S2) and 1:15 (S3). The substrates were digested for thirty-seven days after augmentation with cow rumen liquor. Proximate analysis of the substrates was also done. Biogas was collected using the water displacement method. Results revealed that the total solids (%) of the substrates were 90.12 (P), 96.03 (B), 84.15 (PB1), and 84.94 (PB2). The carbon/nitrogen (C/N) ratios ranged from 9.04 to 15.3. PB1 yielded the highest mean volume of biogas per day (10.8 cm³/day) while P yielded the least (8.07 cm³/day). Results revealed that biogas yields increased as slurry concentration increased. The difference in yields with respect to co-digestion was not significant, whereas the difference with respect to slurry concentration was highly significant. We conclude that the peels of *Musa paradisiaca* and *Phaseolus vulgaris* could be converted into biogas whether digested individually or combined, and that higher slurry concentrations are recommended for a higher production of biogas.

Keywords: Kitchen waste; Slurry concentration; Anaerobic digestion; Co-digestion; Biogas

1. Introduction

Food waste or kitchen wastes are organic fractions of municipal solid wastes that come from left-over food or by-products of food processing. They are mainly sourced from restaurants, canteens, eateries, household kitchens, roadside food vendors and food hawkers (1,2). In most urban cities of developing countries, the indiscriminate disposal of kitchen waste from homes, street food vendors and travelers is worrisome. These wastes deface and pollute major streets and suburbs, and threaten public health, environmental health and safety (3).

Musa paradisiaca (Plantain) is widely cultivated and consumed in various parts of Nigeria. Its fruit and leaves have been used as food for centuries (4). The most popular forms are the roasted unripe fruit and the fried (ripe and unripe) fruit. The peels of this fruit can be used as animal feed or as manure. However, in the urban cities where there may not be livestock to feed nor farms to manure, the peels constitute a waste. This waste needs to be put to a productive use.

* Corresponding author: Justin Chikezie Nnokwe

Phaseolus vulgaris (Beans) is another important food in the tropics. It is a legume that is easily grown in fertile soils, and a very important source of protein (5). Beans is popularly eaten alone or in combination with other foods. The more common preparation of beans is the fried bean cake popularly known as “akara”, and the cooked bean cake known as “moi-moi” in Southeast Nigeria. During the preparation of “akara” and/or “moi-moi”, the outer seed coat of the bean is washed off. This seed coat which is normally used as animal feed where applicable constitutes a waste in urban cities. It therefore needs to be converted to biogas.

Kitchen waste being organic, can be collected and converted through anaerobic digestion (6,7) into biogas (8–10). Biogas is a renewable energy source that can be used for cooking, lighting, and various other uses (11). The potential of converting kitchen waste into biogas is enormous as kitchen waste has high organic content (90-95%), high moisture content (70-90%), and carbon/nitrogen ratio within the required range of 15 to 30 (1). The various forms of kitchen waste can also be combined in a process known as co-digestion (12,13).

The primary purpose of co-digestion is to enhance the carbon/nitrogen (C/N) ratio of the final mixture of the waste for optimal biogas production. Co-digestion may also enhance the faster removal of wastes from the environment, thereby ameliorating the burden of morbidity. Various wastes have been successfully co-digested into biogas [8,10,11].

Another factor of concern in anaerobic digestion is the slurry concentration or substrate-water mixing ratio. If the final mixture is too thick, it might impede biogas flow; if the mixture is too thin, less biogas is produced (14). Therefore, an investigation into the impact of slurry concentration on the efficiency of biogas production is necessary.

Our focus in this work was to first determine if plantain peels and bean peels can be converted into biogas, and then to know the impacts of co-digestion and mixing ratio as it affects biogas production from the substrates during their anaerobic digestion.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1. Collection and Preparation of Samples

Peels of unripe *Musa paradisiaca* (Plantain) and *Phaseolus vulgaris* (Beans) were collected from food vendors at Eziobodo (Owerri-West Local Government Area) and Amakohia-Uratta (Owerri-North Local Government Area) all in Imo State, Nigeria. The peels were air-dried, pulverized, stored in sterile containers, and labeled P and B respectively.

2.2. Proximate analysis

The samples were subjected to proximate analysis to determine moisture content, total solids, protein and carbohydrate content, and carbon-nitrogen (C/N) ratio according to Association of Official Agricultural Chemists (AOAC) 2003 guidelines.

2.3. Preparation of secondary samples

An equal ratio (1:1) of P and B by mass was used to derive PB2. Given the C/N ratios and moisture contents of P and B, a C/N ratio that lies between that of P and B was derived according to (15) to form the sample PB1. The four samples of P, B, PB1, and PB2 were stored in sterile pre-labelled containers.

2.4. Preparation of slurries

One-litre-capacity mini digesters were washed, dried and sterilized at 121 °C for 15 minutes prior to anaerobic digestion. Each digester was air-tight and equipped with a gas outlet hose. The gas outlet opens into a column of water inside an inverted, calibrated plastic measuring cylinder. The measuring cylinder served for both gas storage and daily gas measurement. Biogas was collected using the water displacement method. The total working volume of each digester was 753 cm³. Three slurry concentrations of 1:5 (S1), 1:10 (S2), and 1:15 (S3) substrate-water mixture were prepared in triplicates and aseptically transferred into each digester. To each substrate-water mixture inside a digester, an inoculum of 251 cm³ of freshly strained cow rumen liquor obtained from Obinze abattoir was added, and the final mixture was stirred using a sterile rod. The inoculum represents 33% of the digester volume (16,17). Biogas was measured once a day in repeated measurements for thirty-seven (37) days hydraulic retention time and readings recorded.

2.5. Experimental set-up and design

A randomized complete block design (RCBD) was used as the experimental design.

2.6. Analysis of results

The daily biogas readings were recorded and subsequently analysed using Microsoft Excel 365 Data Analysis Toolpak.

3. Results and Discussion

3.1. Proximate composition of the samples.

The proximate composition of the four samples is presented in Table 1.

Table 1 Proximate composition of P, B, PB1, and PB2

SAMPLE	Code	Moisture content (%)	Ash content (%)	Percent Carbon	Percent Nitrogen	C/N ratio	Total solids (TS) (%)
Plantain	P	9.88	15.59	37.89	2.678	14.138	90.12
Beans	B	3.97	13.15	34.15	3.777	9.043	96.03
Plantain/Beans 1	PB1	15.85	7.88	44.73	3.23	13.85	84.15
Plantain/Beans 2	PB2	15.06	6.49	48.65	3.18	15.3	84.94

The above data agrees with the findings of Meng *et al.* (1) and Bashir *et al.* (18) which suggested that kitchen waste has a high organic content and C/N ratio within the required range. The high total solids of the substrates also agrees with the findings of Kouame *et al.*, (19) in having high total solids which favours methanization. However, we discovered that P, B, and PB1 had C/N ratios lower than 15, but the substrates produced appreciable quantities of biogas as will be seen in subsequent tables. The C/N ratio of plantain peels chaff as observed in this work was lower than that of the work of Makinde and Odokuma (20) and lies closer to the range recommended for methanization.

3.2. Biogas yields of P, B, PB1, and PB2.

Table 2 presents the mean biogas yields for all the substrates.

Table 2 Mean biogas yields for P, B, PB1, and PB2

Slurry Concentrations	S1 (1:6)	S2 (1:11)	S3 (1:16)	Total
P (ml/day)	4.46	1.88	1.73	8.07
B (ml/day)	4.76	3.67	1.41	9.84
PB1 (ml/day)	7.44	1.84	1.52	10.8
PB2 (ml/day)	4.45	2.27	1.49	8.21
Total (ml/day)	21.11	9.66	6.15	36.92

The substrates produced different quantities of biogas after digestion. The substrate combination of PB1 produced the highest mean yield while P had the least mean yield. The co-digestion of plantain and beans peels in the ratio 1:0.691 boosted its biogas yield better than when the substrates were digested in equal proportions or digested alone. This agrees with the findings of Latinwo & Agarry (21) and Olugbemide *et al.* (22) which suggested that co-digestion of substrates produced better yields of biogas. However, there was no significant difference in the yields of the substrates.

In contrast, slurry concentration significantly affected biogas yields from the substrates, whether digested singly or combined (Table 2). The biogas yields increased as substrate concentration increased. The slurry concentrations having one part of the substrate in five parts of water (S1) produced the highest quantities of biogas, followed accordingly by S2 and S3 which produced the least. This result agrees with the findings of Mohamed *et al.* and Deepanraj *et al.* (14,23,24) in having more biogas yields when substrate concentration increases. The summary of Analysis of Variance (ANOVA)

for the substrates is presented in Table 3. The yield differences pertaining to substrates were not significant, while that pertaining to slurry concentration were highly significant. In addition, there was interaction between substrate type and slurry concentration.

Table 3 Summary of two-way ANOVA between P, B, PB1, and PB2

Source of Variation	SS	df	MS	F	P-value	F crit
Substrate (P, B, PB1, PB2)	64.96	3	21.65	0.46	0.71	2.63
Columns (S1, S2, S3)	1131.68	2	565.84	11.99	8.58215E-06	3.02
Interaction	252.42	6	42.07	0.89	0.50	2.12
Within	20392.97	432	47.21			
Total	21842.02	443				

4. Conclusion

We conclude that the co-digestion of plantain and beans chaff has no significant effect on the yield of biogas from kitchen waste, but that slurry concentration significantly affected the yield. Therefore, attention should focus the more on substrate and water mixing ratio to get the best results during anaerobic digestion of kitchen wastes.

Compliance with ethical standards

Disclosure of conflict of interest

No conflict of interest to be disclosed.

References

- [1] Meng Q, Liu H, Zhang H, Xu S, Lichtfouse E, Yun Y. Anaerobic digestion and recycling of kitchen waste: a review. *Environ Chem Lett* 2022 203. 2022 Feb 23;20(3):1745–62.
- [2] Fuqing X, Yangyang L, Xumeng G, Liangcheng Y, Yebo L. Anaerobic digestion of food waste – Challenges and opportunities. *Bioresour Technol*. 2018;247(July 2017):1047–58.
- [3] Giwa AS, Cai H, Memon AG, Segun B, Adie G, Odey EA, et al. Characterization and Environmental Impacts of Kitchen Wastes from Food-Waste Disposer Device. *Environ Eng Manag J*. 2022;21(1):137–44.
- [4] Arvanitoyannis IS, Varzakas TH. Fruit/Fruit Juice Waste Management: Treatment Methods and Potential Uses of Treated Waste. *Waste Manag Food Ind*. 2008;569–628.
- [5] Beebe S, Rao I, Mukankusi C, Buruchara R. Improving resource use efficiency and reducing risk of common bean production in Africa, Latin America, and the Caribbean. 2012;
- [6] Brown D, Li Y. Solid state anaerobic co-digestion of yard waste and food waste for biogas production. *Bioresour Technol*. 2013; 127:275–80.
- [7] Brown D, Shi J, Li Y. Comparison of solid-state to liquid anaerobic digestion of lignocellulosic feedstocks for biogas production. *Bioresour. Technol*. 2012; 124:379–86.
- [8] Morken J, Gjetmundsen M, Fjørtoft K. Determination of kinetic constants from the co-digestion of dairy cow slurry and municipal food waste at increasing organic loading rates. *Renew Energy*. 2018; 117:46–51.
- [9] Xie S, Hai FI, Zhan X, Guo W, Ngo HH, Price WE, et al. Anaerobic co-digestion: A critical review of mathematical modelling for performance optimization. *Bioresour. Technol*. 2016; 222:498–512.
- [10] Pavi S, Kramer LE, Gomes LP, Miranda LAS. Biogas production from co-digestion of organic fraction of municipal solid waste and fruit and vegetable waste. *Bioresour. Technol*. 2017 Mar 1; 228:362–7.
- [11] Hussein AK. Applications of nanotechnology in renewable energies—A comprehensive overview and understanding. *Renew Sustain Energy Rev*. 2015 Feb 1; 42:460–76.

- [12] Koch K, Plabst M, Schmidt A, Helmreich B, Drewes JE. Co-digestion of food waste in a municipal wastewater treatment plant: Comparison of batch tests and full-scale experiences. *Waste Manag.* 2016;47.
- [13] Mata-alvarez J, Dosta J, Romero-güiza MS, Fonoll X, Peces M, Astals S. A critical review on anaerobic co-digestion achievements between 2010 and 2013. *Renew Sustain Energy Rev.* 2014; 36:412–27.
- [14] Deepanraj B, Velmurugan S, Jayaraj S. Solid concentration influence on biogas yield from food waste in an anaerobic batch digester. In: *Proceedings of the 2014 International Conference and Utility Exhibition on Green Energy for Sustainable Development, ICUE 2014.* 2014. p. 10–4.
- [15] C/N Ratio - CORNELL Composting [Internet]. [cited 2023 Oct 3]. Available from: https://compost.css.cornell.edu/calc/cn_ratio.html
- [16] Kawai M, Nagao N, Tajima N, Niwa C, Matsuyama T, Toda T. The effect of the labile organic fraction in food waste and the substrate/inoculum ratio on anaerobic digestion for a reliable methane yield. *Bioresour. Technol.* 2014; 157:174–80.
- [17] Asante-Sackey D, Tetteh EK, Nkosi N, Boakye GO, Ansah AKO, Boamah BB, et al. Effects of inoculum to feedstock ratio on anaerobic digestion for biogas production. *Int J Hydrol.* [Internet]. 2018 [cited 2023 Oct 3]; Volume 2(Issue 5). Available from: <https://medcraveonline.com/IJH/IJH-02-00127.php>
- [18] Bashir Lawal, Oluwatosin Kudirat Shittu, Prince Ossai, Abubakar Asmau. Evaluation of Phytochemicals, Proximate, Minerals and Anti-nutritional Compositions of Yam Peel, Maize Chaff and Bean Coat. *Int J Appl Biol Res.* 2014;6(2):21–37.
- [19] Kouame KKR, Abolle A, Kouakou AR, Gbangbo KR, Ehouman AD, Yao B. Biogas Production from Plantain and Yam Peels: Modelling using Response Surface Methodology. *Earthline J Chem Sci.* 2023 Dec 8;105–19.
- [20] Makinde O, Odokuma L. Comparative Study of the Biogas Potential of Plantain and Yam Peels. *Br J Appl Sci Technol.* 2015 Jan 10;9(4):354–9.
- [21] Modelling the Kinetics of Biogas Production from Mesophilic Anaerobic Co-Digestion of Cow Dung with Plantain Peels | Kayode Latinwo | *International Journal of Renewable Energy Development* [Internet]. [cited 2024 Nov 3]. Available from: <https://ijred.cbiore.id/index.php/ijred/article/view/8181>
- [22] Olugbemide AD, Lajide L, Likozar B, Ighodaro A, Bella-Omunagbe OC, Ifijen IH. Biogas production through anaerobic co-digestion of rice husk and plantain peels: investigation of substrate mixing ratios, digestate quality, and kinetic analysis. *Braz J Chem Eng* [Internet]. 2023 Nov 27 [cited 2024 Nov 3]; Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s43153-023-00415-x>
- [23] Mohamed MS, El-Hadidi YM, El-Bakhshwan MK. Effect of High Total Solids Concentration on Biogas Production from Cattle Dung. *J Soil Sci Agric Eng Mansoura Univ.* 2016;7(10):783–92.
- [24] Deepanraj B, Senthilkumar N, Ranjitha J. Effect of solid concentration on biogas production through anaerobic digestion of rapeseed oil cake. *Energy Sources Part Recovery Util Environ Eff.* 2021 Jun 3;43(11):1329–36.